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Annotatsiya: Maqolada avtomobil sportida psixofizik tayyorgarlik muammolari raqobatbardosh faoliyatning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqilgan. Mezonlarni tanlash va ralli poygachilarining tayyorgarligini optimallashtirish masalalari eng muhim yo'nalishlardandir. Ushbu sport turida tayyorgarlik tizimini takomillashtirish o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Avto rally, jismoniy tayyorgarlik, nazorat, sportchi, psixofizik tayyorgarlik, mashqlar.

Аннотация: В статье рассмотрены проблемы психофизической подготовки в автомобильном спорте, особенности конкурентной деятельности. Важнейшими направлениями являются вопросы выбора критериев и оптимизации подготовки раллистов. Изучено совершенствование системы подготовки в этом виде спорта.

Ключевые слова: Авторалли, физическая подготовка, контроль, спортсмен, психофизическая подготовка, упражнения.

Annotation: The article examines the problems of psychophysical training in motor sports, the peculiarities of competitive activity. The most important areas are the selection of criteria and optimization of rallying training. The improvement of the training system in this sport has been studied.

Key words: Parallels, physical training, control, athlete, psychophysical training, exercises.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, popularization of car sports, as an example of holding sports events in car sports, wide involvement of the young generation in technical and practical sports and promotion of this type of sport are gaining priority.

A number of scientists have conducted studies on the effect of compressive force in motor sports, and it is generated by non-deformable aerodynamic elements, which increases the stability of high-speed vehicles. [1,2,3]

However, in these works, the effect of vibrations was not considered, aerodynamic elements that arise in real conditions of use, stability indicators when passing small-radius curves were not revealed.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.

In the last twenty years, special and scientific methodical literature discussed the issues of improving the psychophysical condition as part of the training of qualified athletes, but these issues were hardly discussed in the special literature devoted to the training of auto pilots. In general, issues of training and control of physical and mental abilities of athletes, which make up the structure of psychophysical training, have been studied the least. [4,5,6,7]

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS.

Thus, the insufficient study of a number of important issues of improving the training of rally racers determined the relevance of the chosen research topic.

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The study and analysis of the traditional option of training auto racers showed that it is relatively low, its effectiveness is insufficient development of a number of important physical and especially psychological qualities in a one-year training cycle. did not ride.

The results of the correlation analysis revealed a high degree of interdependence of the indicators ($n = 0.70-0.92$). Physical (at the level of 100 m running speed and anaerobic threshold - V100 m and VPTDB, respectively) and (psychological training, which evaluates the characteristics of attention, counter-reaction to a moving object time, in accordance with simple and complex sensorimotor reaction) that shows their prognostic value in psychophysical training can show.

In order to experimentally check the possibility of optimizing professional training, Table 1 shows the comparative volumes of the training loads performed by the control and experimental groups A-group Amudarya District Patriotic Organization team and N-group, Nukus private team, respectively. During the experiment, the comparative study of the structure of the psychophysical preparation of the teams revealed that the structure of the psychophysical preparation increased.

Only the results of the two-year follow-up of the experimental groups were determined through didagogical control. 2 types of generalizing factors that had a significant impact on the structure of the psychophysical abilities of racing drivers at different stages of the year gradually decreased. In general, the role of physical fitness and mental endurance has increased.

Among the leading factors that have a significant impact on this are the following:

Gradual volumes of loads performed by athletes of the control (A) and experimental (N) groups

Preparation steps		General preparation			Special preparation		
Groups		A	N	Δ_{A-N}	A	N	Δ_{A-N}
Types of preparation and exercises		time	time	%	time	time	%
Fast	Sprint *	2,8	4,2	+43	6,0	7,2	+20
	Sacrahs *	2,4	2,4	0	2,7	3,0	+11
Endurance	The mode is IPK	3,5	5,0	+43	5,2	8,5	+39
	Mode PTDB	6,2	9,5	+53	14,5	21,5	+48
	Recovery	3,0	3,0	0	8,3	7,0	-16
	Max Power*	4,0	4,0	0	7,0	7,0	0
	Endurance	5,0	5,0	0	12,5	12,5	0
	**	5,4	8,0	+48	11,9	16,0	+35
	Trainers ***	19,0	19,0	0	42,0	42,0	0
	Driving techniques	28	28	0	120	120	0
Total volume stage loads		79,3	87,9	+11	230,1	144,7	244,7

Notes: 1) * – taking into account rest breaks; 2) ** – the same thing, including URM exercises; 3) *** – total working time in all specialized simulators.

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Preparation steps		Initial competitions			Main competitions			In just one year		
Groups		A	N	Δ_{A-N}	A	N	Δ_{A-N}	A	N	Δ_{A-N}
Types of preparation and exercises		time	time	%	time	time	%	time	time	%
Quick power	Sprint *	5,0	5,0	0	3,2	3,2	0	17,0	19,4	+4
	Sacrahs *	1,5	1,7	+13	0	0	0	6,6	7,1	+8
Endurance	Mode	2,8	3,5	+25	0	0	0	11,5	17,0	+48
	IPK	9,1	13,0	+43	2,3	4,5	+49	32,1	48,5	+51
	Mode	6,4	7,5	+17	3,9	5,0	+28	221,6	22,5	+4
Power	PTDB	2,0	2,0	0	0	0	0	13,0	13,0	0
	Recovery	6,0	6,0	0	3,0	3,0	0	26,5	26,5	0
Technical tactician	Maximum	5,4	8,0	+48	0	0	0	22,7	32,0	+41
	strengt h*	15,5	15,5	0	5,0	5,0	0	81,5	81,5	0
	Endurance	104	104	0	68	68	0	320	320	0
Total volume phase loads		157,7	166,2	+5	85,4	88,7	+4	552,5	587,5	+6

Notes: 1) * – taking into account rest breaks; 2) ** – the same thing, including URM exercises; 3) *** – total working time in all specialized simulators.

- 1) integrated psychomotor training (contribution of the generalized factor to the total variance of the sample - 24.64%);
- 2) load tolerance with an important mental component (21.23%);
- 3) general recovery ability of the body (19.48%);
- 4) increased power component of load of concentration ability (18.6%);
- 5) differentiation of intensive aerobic activities (18%);
- 6) the ability to divide and switch attention (14.3%);
- 7) ability to solve problems of increasing complexity (12.82%);
- 8) objects in difficult working conditions (12.54%).

At the end of the scientific experiment, the generalized factor of body recovery played a leading role in the subjects of group A (contribution to the total variance of the sample - 19.48%), and in group N, the factor of tolerance to force load (14.91%).

Figure 2 shows the so-called psychophysical fitness profiles of both groups of racers. A significant superiority of athletes of group A was observed in terms of training indicators such as recovery from loads in different directions (numbers 12-15), as well as psychomotor indicators

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(numbers 17-28). The data of this scientific experience show the high selectivity of the effect of specialized preparations.

Conclusion: During the pedagogical experience, the following relative increase in the physical fitness indicators of the athletes of the A, N-groups was determined.

Reliable relative changes in speed indicators in group A reached 2.33% compared to 1.42% in group N. The values of the relative changes in the parameters describing endurance in the experimental group were 2.76–5.23% compared to 1.05–3.93% in subjects.

The change in strength indicators in both groups was approximately the same, 5.11–14.5% in the experimental group and 4.85–16.8% in the control group.

According to indicators describing recovery processes, the athletes of group A achieved a decisive advantage. Subjects of this group had a reliable increase from 6.4 to 13.6%, while in the N-group, the relative changes were unreliable and amounted to 2.2-2.7%.

The high level of correlation of indicators of physical (V100 m, V PTDB) and psychological training (attention) allows them to be used as informative indicators of psychophysical training of racing drivers.

The use of the experimental methodology of purposefully changing the volume of loads in physical and psychological directions ensured acceptability in relation to competitive activities. specialized psychological (on average 40%) abilities of drivers allowed to increase the endurance level of rally driver training components up to 5%, and psychological preparation up to 13%.

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